

Lignocellulolytic activities of culturable marine woodborers' gut microbiota

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Abstract

In this study, pure bacterial and fungal isolates obtained by culturing inoculum from woodborers' gut were induced to produce lignocellulolytic enzymes in a variety of substrates and their lignocellulolytic activities investigated. The inocula were obtained from woodborers *Dicyathifer manni* (Wright, 1866), *Sphaeroma terebrans* (Bate, 1866) and *Cirolana* sp. The cultures used enrichment media containing ground *Rhizophora mucronata* wood, filter paper, carboxyl methylcellulose, avicel cellulose, beechwood xylan and cellobiose as sole carbon sources. The microorganisms showed generally low ligninolytic activities but commendable cellulolytic and hemicellulolytic activities. β -glucosidase and xylanase activities were the highest activities exhibited by both bacterial and fungal isolates. The highest was bacterial β -glucosidase activity (94.55 U/ml) shown by *Lysinibacillus boronitolerans* from *S. terebrans* gut cultured in a medium containing avicel cellulose. Xylanase activity was also relatively high (up to 91.7U/ml) cultured in media containing cellobiose and xylan. The fungal isolate with the highest cellulolytic activity was β -glucosidase activity of 38.34 U/ml shown by *Aspergillus niger* obtained from the gut of *S. terebrans* and cultured in a medium containing avicel cellulose as a sole carbon source. Avicel cellulose, cellobiose and xylan beech wood were found to be best inducers of cellulase and hemicellulase production. *Lysinibacilli* and *Aspergilli* in this study present interesting advantages that make them good models for studying physiological approaches to enzyme production and lignocellulose degradation.

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Introduction

There are three groups of marine woodborers along the Indian coasts. These are Shipworms, Piddocks and Pill Bugs (Santhakumaran, 1996). Shipworms belonging to Family Teredinidae, are molluscs in class bivalvia (Turner, 1966; Turner, 1971). Piddocks, are also molluscs Family Pholadidae class bivalvia (Turner, 1971). The Pill Bugs on the other hand are arthropods in the class crustacean, order is opoda and family Sphaeromatidae (Pillai, 1961). Three species of woodborer belonging to two of the above-mentioned groups were encountered in this study. They were identified in our earlier work as *Dicyathifer mannii* (Wright, 1866) belong to phylum Molusca, class bivalvia, family Teredinidae; *Sphaeroma terebrans* (Bate, 1866) belong to phylum Arthropoda, class crustacea, family Sphaeromatidae; and *Cirolana sp.* belonging to phylum Arthropoda, class crustacea, family Cirolanidae (Bosire *et al.*, 2015). The culturable marine woodborers' gut microbiota in this study were both bacterial and fungal isolates obtained from the above-mentioned marine woodborers' gut inocula. 16S rRNA and ITS gene barcoding identified them respectively, in our earlier work (Bosire *et al.*, 2013a). Four strains of bacteria were identified as *Lysinibacillus boronitolerans* (from *D. mannii* and *S. terebrans*), *Lysinibacillus fusiformis* (from *S. terebrans* and *Cirolana sp.*), *Lysinibacillus sphaericus* and *Lysinibacillus xylanilyticus* (both from *Cirolana sp.*). Fungal isolates were identified as *Aspergillus niger* (from *D. mannii* and *S. terebrans*), *Neosartorya fischeri*, *A. fumigatus* and *Penicillium sp.* (from *D. mannii*), *Botryotinia fuckeliana* (from *S. terebrans*), *A. costaricaensis* and *A. fumigatus* (from *Cirolana sp.*).

Lignocellulose is the major structural component of plants composed of a mixture of carbohydrate polymers (cellulose and hemicellulose) tightly bound to lignin, a complex polymer of phenyl propanoid molecules (Lee, 1997). Wood, grass, agricultural, forest and urban solid wastes all contain lignocellulose.

Lignin is degradable by lignin peroxidase (LiP), Mn-dependent peroxidase (MnP), and laccase (Lac) or mono-phenol oxidase (Vaaje-Kolstad *et al.*, 2010; Bugg *et al.*, 2011; Majumdar *et al.*, 2014; Beeson *et al.*, 2015 and Pollegioni *et al.* 2015). Complete enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose requires endo- β -1, 4-D- glucanase (EC 3.2.1.4), exo- β -1, 4-D-glucanase or exo- β -1, 4-D-cellobiohydrolase (EC 3.2.1.91) and β -glucosidase (EC 3.2.1.21) (de Vries and Visser, 2001; de Vries, 2003; Watanabe and Tokuda, 2010; van den Brink and de Vries, 2011 and Payne *et al.*, 2015). Complete degradation of xylan heteropolymer requires endoxylanase (EC 3.2.1.8), β -xylosidase (EC 3.2.1.37), acetylxylan esterase (EC 3.1.1.72), L-arabinose releasing enzymes such as α -L-arabinofuranosidase (EC 3.2.1.55) and arabinoxylan arabinofuranohydrolase, α -glucuronidase (EC 3.2.1.139), feruloyl esterase, and *p*-coumaroyl esterase (Sunna and Antranikian, 1997; Gregory *et al.*, 1998). Cellulases and hemicellulases are produced by a number of microbes, including fungi and bacteria (Beguin, 1990; Pauly *et al.*, 1999; de Souza, 2013; Busk and Lange, 2015).

The major constituents in lignocellulose enzyme hydrolysates are glucose and xylose released from cellulose and hemicellulose, respectively (Himmel, 2007; Hahn-Hagerdal *et al.*, 2007; Galazka *et al.*, 2010, and de Souza, 2013). The fermentation of the sugars from these hydrolysates generates products such as ethanol, acetone, butanol, glycerol, acetic acid, citric acid and fumaric acid (Howard *et al.*, 2003; Madson and Tereck, 2004). Ethanol and butanol produced from degraded and fermented lignocellulose can be used as biofuels (Sun and Cheng, 2002). Bioethanol converted from edible sources such as corns and sugarcane is called first-generation bioethanol (FGB), whereas that produced from non-food sources is called second-generation bioethanol (SGB). The latter offers great promise to replace fossil fuels without causing the feud of food-fuel supply as they are derived from non-edible sources such as lignocellulose biomass (Tengerdy and Szakacs, 2003; Tan *et al.*, 2008; Chun *et al.*, 2010).

Biofuels are emerging as a promising option with which to cope with climate change and a diminishing oil supply (Goldemberg and Coelho, 2004; Jun-Seok *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, the focus of the present work was to explore the lignocellulolytic activities of culturable bacteria and fungi from the gut of woodborers *D. mannii*, *S. terebrans* and *Cirolana sp.* The enzymes could find application in lignocellulosic biomass bioconversion industries especially bioethanol production.

Materials and methods

Chemicals (Enzymes, Substrates, Buffers and Reagents)

Laccase (from *Trametes versicolor*), Mn-dependent peroxidase (MnP), lignin peroxidase (LiP), β -glucosidase from *Aspergillus niger*, p-Nitrophenyl β -D-glucopyranose (pNPG), 4-hydroxy-3, 5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde azine (syringaldazine), D (+)- xylose, microcrystalline cellulose (Avicel PH101), carboxy methylcellulose (CMC) sodium salt, D (+)- cellobiose, 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl alcohol (veratryl alcohol), PMSF (phenyl methyl sulfonyl flouride), sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA), and beech wood xylan were all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. All other chemicals were of analytical grade.

Enzyme Production Induction of Microorganisms from the Gut of the Woodborers

One *D. mannii*, three *S. terebrans*, and three *Cirolana sp.* were surface sterilized with 70% ethanol, rinsed in distilled water and allowed to air dry for 1 minute. Under aseptic conditions, the entire gut of *D. mannii* and the guts of the 2 isopod species were separately removed with a blade and a pair of tweezers and mixed with 1 ml 0.85% sodium chloride to obtain inoculums.

Bacteria were cultivated in nutrient agar and subsequent culturing and plating carried out to obtain pure colonies. Fungi were cultivated on sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) medium solidified with 1.6% w/v agar. They were incubated at 30°C for 2-5 days.

A single agar disc was cut from the actively growing colony margin of a culture to inoculate each assay medium in subsequent culturing and plating to isolate pure colonies.

The bacteria and fungi above were induced to produce lignocellulolytic enzymes by culturing them in enrichment media containing ground *Rhizophora mucronata* wood, filter paper, carboxy methylcellulose, avicel cellulose, beech wood xylan and cellobiose as sole carbon sources. Crude enzyme extracts from these micro organisms were screened for lignocellulolytic activities and the activities compared between different carbon sources.

The bacterial isolates were cultured in liquid culture medium containing 0.1M citrate-phosphate buffer, 5 g/L carbon source (carboxyl methylcellulose sodium salt (CMC)/ filter paper/ beech wood xylan/*R. mucronata* wood dust/cellobiose/avicel cellulose) and 0.2g/L yeast extract. The cultures were incubated at 37°C for 3 days. Solubilisation of insoluble carbon sources indicated degrading activity. Proteinase inhibitor PMSF (phenyl methyl sulfonylflouride) was added to the culture media. The media were homogenized and centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 30 minutes at 4°C and the supernatant (crude extract) stored at -20°C.

The fungal isolate were cultured in liquid medium containing 0.1M citrate-phosphate buffer, pH 4, 10g/L yeast nitrogen base and 5 g/L carbon source (carboxyl methylcellulose sodium salt (CMC)/filter paper/beech wood xylan/*R. mucronata* wood dust/cellobiose/avicel cellulose). Solubilisation of insoluble carbon sources indicated degrading activity. Proteinase inhibitor PMSF was added to the culture media. The culture media were homogenized and centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 30 minutes at 4°C and the supernatant (crude extract) stored at -20°C. The extracts were used in determination of lignocellulolytic activities.

Determination of Lignocellulolytic Activities of Woodborers' Gut Microbiota

Determination of Ligninolytic Activity of the Extract

Ligninolytic activities were determined spectrophotometrically using a Beckman Coulter™ UV/VIS spectrophotometer (DU® 530 Life Science). The least count of absorbance measurement was 0.001 (Risna and Suhurma, 2002; Sahay *et al.*, 2008; Yadav *et al.*, 2009; Singh *et al.*, 2011).

Lignin peroxidase (LiP) was determined by the peroxide-dependent oxidation of 10mm veratryl alcohol to veratraldehyde in 125mM tart rate buffer, pH 3.0 with 2mM H₂O₂ (controls without H₂O₂ were included), according to Orth *et al.* (1993). The molar extinction coefficient value of 9300 M⁻¹ Cm⁻¹ for veratraldehyde at 310nm was used for calculating the enzyme units. All enzyme assays were carried out in triplicate. The results were also interpreted as percent discoloration compared to the control calculated as $(A_{310} \text{ for control} - A_{310} \text{ for test}) / A_{310} \text{ for control} \times 100$ (Denise *et al.*, 1996).

Manganese-dependent peroxidases (MnP) was assayed by oxidation of phenol red, which was measured by monitoring the A₆₁₀ ($\epsilon = 22.0 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at room temperature (Camarero *et al.*, 1999; Salame *et al.*, 2012). The reaction mixture contained 250mM lactate, 2mM MnSO₄, 0.5% bovine serum albumin, 1mg/ml of phenol red, and 0.5 ml of supernatant in 20mm sodium succinate buffer (pH 4.5) in a total volume of 1ml. The reaction was initiated by the addition of H₂O₂ to final concentration of 2mm and was stopped after 1min with 50µl of 10% NaOH. Omitting MnSO₄ from the reaction mixture carried out control assays of phenol red oxidation in the absence of Mn²⁺. MnP activity was calculated by subtracting the value for phenol red-oxidizing activity in the absence of Mn²⁺ from the value for the activity obtained in the presence of manganese. All enzyme assays were carried out in triplicate.

Laccase (Lac) was analyzed by monitoring the oxidation of 0.25mM syringaldazine in 100mM citrate-phosphate buffer at pH 5.2 (Fakoussa and Frost, 1999; Lopez *et al.*, 2007). Heat inactivated (100°C for 15min) supernatant and enzyme substrate controls were included. Lac activity was determined by the increase in the absorbance due to the formation of tetramethoxy-azo-bis-methylene quinone, resulting from the oxidation of syringaldazine as described by Leonowicz and Grzywnowickz (1981). The activity was assayed in mixed reactions containing supernatant, citrate-phosphate buffer (pH 5.2, 0.1M) and syringaldazine 0.25mm in methanol. An increase in absorbance at 530 nm ($\epsilon = 65000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was followed at 25°C to determine laccase activity in international units (IU) (Salmones and Mata, 2002). All enzyme assays were carried out in triplicate.

All ligninolytic enzyme activity was expressed as IU/ml. An international unit IU (or U) is defined as the amount of enzyme activity, which catalysed the transformation of 1 micromole of substrate per minute under standard conditions. This was calculated using the formula:

Enzyme Activity (U/ml) = $(A \cdot V) / (t \cdot \epsilon \cdot v)$, where A = Absorbance at corresponding wavelength, V = Total volume of reaction mixture (ml), v = enzyme volume (ml), t = Incubation time (min) and ϵ = Corresponding Extinction Coefficient (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) (Desai *et al.*, 2011).

Determination of Cellulolytic Activity of the Extract

The crude extract was assayed for cellulose activity by incubating crude enzyme solution with substrate and measuring amount of reducing sugar released. For general cellulase (FPase) activity, the substrate was What man No. 1 filter paper in 0.05M sodium citrate buffer (pH 4.8).

For CMCase (endoglucanase) and avicelase (exoglucanase) activity determination, the substrates were 1% (w/v) CMC sodium salt and

1 % avicel cellulose respectively, in 50mM sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.0). Boiling at 100°C for 15 min stopped the reactions. The amount of reducing sugar released was determined by the dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) method (Miller, 1959). Heat inactivated (100°C for 15min) supernatant and enzyme substrate controls were included. Glucosidase activity was assayed with pNPG as the substrate according to Chen *et al.* (2010). All the enzyme assays were carried out in triplicate.

One unit of cellulase activity is defined as the amount of enzyme that released 1 μ mol/ml of glucose equivalents per min (Libmond and Savoie, 1993). Glucose was used as standard.

Determination of Hemicellulolytic Activity of the Extract

The crude enzyme extract was assayed for xylanase activity by incubating 0.1 ml of crude enzyme solution with 0.1ml of 0.5% (wt v⁻¹) Beech wood xylan freshly suspended in 0.1M pH 5.5 acetate buffer. The reaction mixture was incubated at 40°C for 30min and then completed to 1.0ml by adding 0.8ml distilled water (Sherief *et al.*, 2010). The amount of reducing sugar released was determined by DNS method (Miller, 1959) against boiled enzyme using D-xylose as standard. All enzyme assays were carried out in triplicate. One unit of xylanase is defined as the amount of enzyme that catalyzed the release of one μ mole of D-xylose per ml per min under the assay conditions.

Results

Ligninolytic Activity Assays

There was generally low lignin modifying enzyme activity in both bacterial and fungal isolates (data not shown).

Cellulolytic and Hemicellulolytic Activities of the Crude Extracts

Both bacterial and fungal isolates exhibited endoglucanase, avicelase (exoglucanase), β -glucosidase and filter paper (FPase) activities.

Cellulolytic and Hemicellulolytic Activities of the Crude Bacterial Extract

Bacterial isolates showed significantly high cellulolytic (β -glucosidase) and hemicellulolytic (xylanase) activities. β -glucosidase activity was the highest (94.55 U/ml) shown by *S. terebrans* isolate 1 (*L. boronitolerans*) cultured in a medium containing avicel cellulose substrate as a carbon source.

Xylanase activity was also relatively high (up to 91.7 U/ml) by isolates in media containing cellobiose and xylan beech wood substrates. Highest xylanase activity was shown by all the 3 bacteria species (*L. fusiformis*, *L. xylanilyticus* and *L. sphaericus*) isolated from *Cirolana sp.* in media containing cellobiose substrate (Table 1).

β -Glucosidase production was induced in all the substrates used while xylanase was induced moderately in *R. mucronata* wood dust and FP and but highly induced in xylan (2 isolates) and cellobiose substrates.

All the bacteria isolates from the 3 woodborers showed an appreciably high xylanase induction in media containing cellobiose substrate (Fig. 1).

Table 1. Cellulolytic and Hemicellulolytic Activity of Bacterial Isolates.

Culture	Isolate	β -Glucosidase	Xylanase
C ₁ W	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	11.86 \pm 0.22	11.03 \pm 0.34
C ₂ W	<i>L. xylanilyticus</i>	28.92 \pm 0.06	13.43 \pm 0.3
C ₃ W	<i>L. sphaericus</i>	4.64 \pm 0.08	11.32 \pm 0.22
D ₁ W	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	17.9 \pm 4.9	13.32 \pm 0.45
S ₂ F	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	9.53 \pm 0.35	13.21 \pm 0.4
S ₃ F	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	11.25 \pm 0.18	2.21 \pm 0.25
C ₂ F	<i>L. xylanilyticus</i>	10.51 \pm 0.46	-
C ₃ F	<i>L. sphaericus</i>	13.9 \pm 0.75	0.55 \pm 0.29
S ₁ CM	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	19 \pm 0.38	0.59 \pm 0.34

Culture	Isolate	β -Glucosidase	Xylanase
S ₂ CM	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	31.57 \pm 0.43	0.51 \pm 0.25
C ₂ CM	<i>L. xylanilyticus</i>	11.92 \pm 0.25	0.52 \pm 0.26
S ₁ A	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	94.55 \pm 8.35	0.5 \pm 0.25
S ₃ A	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	13.64 \pm 0.76	-
C ₁ A	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	14.62 \pm 0.37	0.49 \pm 0.24
D ₁ A	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	15.84 \pm 0.23	11.12 \pm 0.25
S ₂ X	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	10.45 \pm 0.08	-
C ₂ X	<i>L. xylanilyticus</i>	10.92 \pm 0.17	-
C ₃ X	<i>L. sphaericus</i>	3.79 \pm 0.08	79.71 \pm 0.8
D ₁ X	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	22.39 \pm 0.7	89.4 \pm 1.43
S ₁ CE	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	27.31 \pm 0.59	79.78 \pm 0.13
S ₂ CE	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	29.77 \pm 3.07	88.66 \pm 0.46
S ₃ CE	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	6.31 \pm 0.18	88.6 \pm 0.39
C ₁ CE	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	1.55 \pm 0.11	90.14 \pm 1.18
C ₂ CE	<i>L. xylanilyticus</i>	1.5 \pm 0.06	91.7 \pm 1.35
C ₃ CE	<i>L. sphaericus</i>	28.57 \pm 0.71	90.44 \pm 1.43
D ₁ CE	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	8.4 \pm 0.55	84.37 \pm 2.22

Data is Mean of triplicates (U/ml); bacterial isolates from the gut of woodborers *D. Dicyathifer manii*; *S. Sphaeroma terebrans* and *C. cirolana sp.*; cultured in media containing substrates W, wood; CM, carboxymethylcellulose; A, avicel cellulose; X, xylan beechwood and CE, cellobiose. (-) No activity.

Fig. 1. β -glucosidase and Xylanase Activities of the Crude Supernatants.

Comparison of β -glucosidase and xylanase activities (U/ml) of the crude supernatants of bacterial cultures grown in enrichment media containing 0.5% (w/v) *Rhizophora* wood dust, CMC, FP, Avicel®, xylan beech wood and cellobiose as sole carbon sources. U = μ mol reducing sugar produced/min.

Cellulolytic and Hemicellulolytic Activities of the Crude Fungal Extract

Inducement of cellulolytic and hemicellulolytic enzyme production by fungal isolates on a number of substrates was successful. Their activities were however relatively lower compared to bacterial isolates. They showed significantly high cellulolytic (CMCase or endoglucanase and β -glucosidase) activities and hemicellulolytic (xylanase) activity.

The fungal isolate with the highest cellulolytic activity was β -glucosidase activity of 38.34 U/ml shown by *A. niger* obtained from the gut of *S. terebrans* and cultured in a medium containing avicel as a sole carbon source.

The next highest β -glucosidase activity was by another *A. niger* strain (33.62 U/ml) also from *S. terebrans* cultured in medium containing xylan beech wood substrate. The highest xylanase activity (17.02 U/ml) was exhibited by yet another *A. niger* strain from *D. mannii* cultured in a medium containing cellobiose, whereas the highest CMCase activity (14.14 U/ml) was exhibited by *A. costaricaensis* from *Cirolana* cultured in a medium containing xylan beech wood (Table 2).

FPase and Avicelase activities were very low in all the fungal isolates (data not shown).

Table 2. Cellulolytic and Hemicellulolytic Activity of Fungal Isolates.

Culture	Isolate	CMCase	β -glucosidase	Xylanase
S ₁ CM	<i>A. niger</i>	3.57 ± 0.67	0.44 ± 0.01	10.58 ± 0.56
S ₁ A	<i>A. niger</i>	2.35 ± 0.14	16.84 ± 2.22	2.37 ± 0.25
S ₂ A	<i>A. niger</i>	2.33 ± 0.15	18.87 ± 0.61	3.09 ± 0.03
S ₃ A	<i>A. niger</i>	0.7 ± 0.36	38.34 ± 0.56	2.44 ± 0.22
S ₄ A	<i>B. fuckeliana</i>	1.46 ± 0.2	11.32 ± 0.3	3.33 ± 0.22
S ₅ A	<i>A. niger</i>	9.33 ± 0.88	14.18 ± 0.28	1.56 ± 0.11
C ₁ A	<i>A. costaricaensis</i>	1.42 ± 0.03	19.6 ± 0.39	1.61 ± 0.53
C ₂ A	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	0.12 ± 0.05	17.76 ± 0.5	0.89 ± 0.44
D ₂ A	<i>A. niger</i>	2.87 ± 0.08	17.6 ± 1.81	2.66 ± 0.22
D ₅ A	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	2.48 ± 0.28	16.69 ± 0.61	2.37 ± 0.25
S ₁ X	<i>A. niger</i>	7.36 ± 0.61	17.78 ± 0.08	13.84 ± 1.43
S ₂ X	<i>A. niger</i>	10.6 ± 0.53	33.62 ± 1.8	11.77 ± 0.59
S ₃ X	<i>A. niger</i>	10.66 ± 0.51	6.11 ± 0.61	11.92 ± 0.72
S ₄ X	<i>B. fuckeliana</i>	9.7 ± 0.28	16.21 ± 0.24	12.8 ± 0.56
S ₅ X	<i>A. niger</i>	11.55 ± 0.4	8.37 ± 0.56	14.65 ± 0.45
C ₁ X	<i>A. costaricaensis</i>	14.14 ± 0.28	20.72 ± 0.37	13.32 ± 1.11
C ₂ X	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	11.01 ± 0.7	21.22 ± 0.65	10.21 ± 1.18
D ₁ X	<i>A. niger</i>	7.25 ± 0.56	21.09 ± 0.56	14.5 ± 1.12
D ₂ X	<i>A. niger</i>	9.51 ± 0.57	17.19 ± 0.65	11.54 ± 0.59
D ₃ X	<i>N. fischeri</i>	11.32 ± 1.18	14.15 ± 0.25	0.93 ± 0.17
D ₄ X	<i>A. niger</i>	10.4 ± 1.68	14.4 ± 1.51	11.69 ± 0.56
D ₅ X	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	9.51 ± 0.57	18.67 ± 0.2	4.22 ± 0.22
S ₁ CE	<i>A. niger</i>	7.88 ± 0.59	15.76 ± 0.3	15.77 ± 0.23
S ₂ CE	<i>A. niger</i>	1.41 ± 0.28	18.65 ± 0.19	11.1 ± 1.11
S ₃ CE	<i>A. niger</i>	0.11 ± 0.03	13.45 ± 0.16	16.36 ± 0.9
S ₄ CE	<i>B. fuckeliana</i>	0.43 ± 0.59	12.81 ± 0.09	12.73 ± 0.34
S ₅ CE	<i>A. niger</i>	1.67 ± 0.56	14.66 ± 0.33	10.51 ± 0.56
C ₁ CE	<i>A. costaricaensis</i>	0.22 ± 0.06	15.46 ± 0.12	5.03 ± 0.56
C ₂ CE	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	0.13 ± 0.03	11.72 ± 0.1	7.4 ± 1.7
D ₁ CE	<i>A. niger</i>	0.13 ± 0.04	16.05 ± 0.21	13.99 ± 0.59
D ₂ CE	<i>A. niger</i>	0.14 ± 0.03	18.17 ± 0.13	17.02 ± 0.92
D ₃ CE	<i>N. fischeri</i>	0.88 ± 0.2	18.72 ± 0.29	15.32 ± 0.8
D ₄ CE	<i>A. niger</i>	0.13 ± 0.04	21.93 ± 0.36	14.65 ± 1.18
D ₅ CE	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	0.13 ± 0.03	15.3 ± 0.26	16.06 ± 0.56

Data is Mean of triplicates (U/ml); fungal isolates from the gut of woodborers D, *Dicyathifer manii*; S, *Sphaeroma terebrans* and C, *cirolana sp.*; cultured in media containing substrates CM, carboxymethylcellulose; A, avicel cellulose; X, xylan (beech wood) and CE, cellobiose.

While avicel cellulose, xylan bech wood and cellobiose substrates showed sufficient inducement of CMC_{ase}, β-glucosidase and xylanase production by many fungal isolates, CMC showed. sufficient inducement of only *A. niger* from *S. terebrans* gut. Interestingly, CMC_{ase} (endoglucanase) production was

significantly induced by xylan beech wood substrate (Fig. 2). Fungal isolates grew slowly in media containing

R. mucronata wood and FP as a sole carbon source. The resulting enzyme activities of these cultures were very low (data not shown).

Fig. 2. Activities of the Crude Fungal Supernatants.

Comparison of CMC_{ase} (endoglucanase), β-glucosidase and xylanase activities (U/ml) of the crude supernatants of fungal cultures grown in enrichment media containing 0.5% (w/v) Avicel®, CMC or xylan beech wood and cellobiose as sole carbon sources. U = μmol reducing sugar produced/min.

Discussion

In this study, pure bacterial and fungal isolates obtained by culturing inoculum from woodborers gut were induced to produce lignocellulolytic enzymes in a variety of substrates and their lignocellulolytic activities were investigated. The cultures used enrichment media containing ground *R. mucronata* wood dust, filter paper, CMC, avicel cellulose, beech wood xylan and cellobiose as sole carbon sources.

The micro organisms showed generally low ligninolytic activities but commendable cellulolytic and hemicellulolytic activities. This is in agreement with a similar study using soil fungal strain on wheat straw as a model agro-waste substrate by solid-state fermentation (Acharya *et al.*, 2010). The study showed a low MnP activity of between 0.108

± 0.031 U/g and 2.849 ± 0.143 U/g but high cellulolytic and hemicellulolytic activities of between 0.424U/g and 84.87U/g. β -glucosidase and xylanase activities were the highest activities exhibited by both bacterial and fungal isolates in our study (Table 3). The highest was bacterial β -glucosidase activity (94.55U/ml) shown by *L. boronitolerans* from *S. terebrans* gutcultured in a medium containing avicel cellulose. Xylanase activity was also relatively high (up to 91.7U/ml) cultured in media containing cellobiose and xylan.

The fungal isolate with the highest cellulolytic activity was β -glucosidase activity of 38.34 U/ml shown by *A. niger* obtained from the gut of *S. terebrans* and cultured in a medium containing avicel as a sole carbon source.

Table 3. Activity maxima of woodborers' gut microbiota.

Culture	Substrate	Isolate	Activity	Units (U/ml)	\pm	SD
S ₁ A	Avicel	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	β -glucosidase	94.55	\pm	8.35
C ₂ CE	Cellobiose	<i>L. xylanilyticus</i>	Xylanase	91.70	\pm	1.35
C ₃ CE	Cellobiose	<i>L. sphaericus</i>	Xylanase	90.44	\pm	1.43
C ₁ CE	Cellobiose	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	Xylanase	90.14	\pm	1.18
D ₁ X	Xylan	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	Xylanase	89.40	\pm	1.43
S ₂ CE	Cellobiose	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	Xylanase	88.66	\pm	0.46
S ₃ CE	Cellobiose	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	Xylanase	88.60	\pm	0.39
D ₁ CE	Cellobiose	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	Xylanase	84.37	\pm	2.22
S ₁ CE	Cellobiose	<i>L. boronitolerans</i>	Xylanase	79.78	\pm	0.13
C ₃ X	Xylan	<i>L. sphaericus</i>	Xylanase	79.71	\pm	0.80
S ₃ A	Avicel	<i>A. niger</i>	β -glucosidase	38.34	\pm	0.56
S ₂ X	Xylan	<i>A. niger</i>	β -glucosidase	33.62	\pm	1.80
S ₂ CM	CMC	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	β -glucosidase	31.57	\pm	0.43
S ₂ CE	Cellobiose	<i>L. fusiformis</i>	β -glucosidase	29.77	\pm	3.07
C ₂ W	Wood	<i>L. xylanilyticus</i>	β -glucosidase	28.92	\pm	0.06
C ₃ CE	Cellobiose	<i>L. sphaericus</i>	β -glucosidase	28.57	\pm	0.71
D ₂ CE	Cellobiose	<i>A. niger</i>	Xylanase	17.02	\pm	0.92
S ₃ CE	Cellobiose	<i>A. niger</i>	Xylanase	16.36	\pm	0.9
D ₅ CE	Cellobiose	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	Xylanase	16.06	\pm	0.56
S ₁ CE	Cellobiose	<i>A. niger</i>	Xylanase	15.77	\pm	0.23
D ₃ CE	Cellobiose	<i>N. fischeri</i>	Xylanase	15.32	\pm	0.80

Data is Mean of triplicates (U/ml); bacterial and fungal isolates from the gut of woodborers *D*, *Dicyathifer manii*; *S*, *Sphaeroma terebrans* and *C*, *cirolana sp.*; cultured in media containing substrates CM, carboxy methylcellulose; A, avicel cellulose; X, xylan (beech wood); CE, cellobiose; and W, *Rhizophora mucronata* wood dust.

Our study showed *A. niger* β -glucosidase activity of between 0.44U/ml to 38.34U/ml, endoglucanase 0.11U/ml to 11.15U/ml, and xylanase 0.89U/ml to 17.02U/ml. FPase and exoglucanase activities were the lowest. In another study (Acharya *et al.*, 2010),

lignocellulolytic soil fungal strains activity profile using wheat straw as a model agro-waste by solid-state fermentation showed *A. niger* activities of β -glucosidase 6.171U/g to 9.259U/g, endoglucanase 15.43U/g to 64.811U/g, xylanase 11.102U/g to 84.87U/g and FPase 3.858U/g to 9.259U/g.

Exoglucanase showed the lowest activity of 0.424U/g to 0.831. Both studies implicate *A. niger* as a potent lignocellulolytic fungi.

The filamentous fungus *A. niger* is known to produce a wide range of hemicellulose-degrading enzymes and it has been used for many industrial applications. Our study confirms its consideration as one of the most important microorganism for cellulase/hemicellulase production.

It constitutes the source of these enzymes for industrial applications, including the production of biofuels from plant biomass (de Souza, 2013). This study discovered that fungal isolates grew slowly in media containing *R. macronata* wood and FP as a sole carbon source. The resulting enzyme activities of these cultures were very low, indicating that wood and FP were not good carbon sources for the inducement of production of cellulolytic and hemicellulolytic enzymes from the isolates.

Cellulolytic bacteria have been reported in different genus such as *Clostridium*, *Ruminococcus*, *Caldicellulosiruptor*, *Butyrivibrio*, *Acetivibrio*, *Cellulomonas*, *Erwinia*, *Thermobifida*, *Fibrobacter*, *Cytophaga*, and *Sporocytophaga*. Bacterial degradation of cellulolytic material is more restricted to biomass containing low amounts of lignin, since bacteria are poor producers of ligninases (Lynd *et al.*, 2002). This explains the low inducement by *R. mucronata* wood and FP substrates in this study, which have high lignin content.

The low ligninolytic activities in our study could be due to use of single cultures. Co-culturing could improve inducement of production of ligninases, cellulases and hemicelluloses. Noratiqah *et al.*, 2016 reported four micro organisms from *Bulbitermes* sp. termite gut (A1, B1, B2, and Br3) with high lignocellulolytic enzyme activity. They were identified as *Aspergillus* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Bacillus* sp. and *Brevibacillus* sp., respectively.

Aspergillus sp. A1 showed highest activities of lignin peroxidase (729.12 U/g) and β -glucosidase (22.97 U/g). The highest endoglucanase (138.77 U/g) and manganese peroxidase (47.73 U/g) activity were observed in *Bacillus* sp. B1. The *Bacillus* sp. B2 produced highest activities of exoglucanase (32.16U/g) and laccase (71.18U/g). The highest xylanase (104.96U/g) activity was observed in *Brevibacillus* sp. Br3. The production of enzymes particularly endoglucanase, β -glucosidase, xylanase, lignin peroxidase and laccase were approximate 17-93% higher in co-culture compared to single culture. Their findings suggested that saw dust can be used as a cheap renewable raw material for the induction of production of lignocellulolytic enzymes. The study also indicated that the fungal-bacterial co-culture could be a good alternative for the enzymes production.

Bacterial isolates in this study showed significantly high cellulolytic (β -glucosidase) and hemicellulolytic (xylanase) activities. β -glucosidase activity was the highest (94.55U/ml) shown by *L. boronitolerans* cultured in a medium containing avicel cellulose substrate as a carbon source. Xylanase activity was also relatively high (up to 91.7U/ml) by isolates in media containing cellobiose and xylan beech wood substrates. Highest xylanase activity was shown by all the 3 bacteria species (*L. fusiformis*, *L. xylanilyticus* and *L. sphaericus*) in media containing cellobiose substrate.

Inducement of cellulolytic and hemicellulolytic enzyme production by fungal isolates on a number of substrates was relatively lower compared to bacterial isolates. They showed significantly high cellulolytic (CMCase or endoglucanase and β -glucosidase) activities and hemicellulolytic (xylanase) activity. The fungal isolate with the highest cellulolytic activity was β -glucosidase activity of 38.34U/ml shown by *A. niger* cultured in a medium containing avicel as a sole carbon source. The next highest β -glucosidase activity was by another *A. niger* strain (33.62U/ml) cultured in medium containing xylan beech wood substrate.

The highest xylanase activity (17.02U/ml) was exhibited by yet another *A. niger* strain cultured in a medium containing cellobiose, whereas the highest CMCase activity (14.14U/ml) was exhibited by *A. costaricensis* from *Cirolana* sp. cultured in a medium containing xylan beech wood.

This showed that both bacterial and fungal isolates were induced to produce enzymes by the various substrates used and the highest induction was by avicel cellulose, cellobiose and xylan beech wood.

The biochemistry of the process behind lignocellulosic degradation has been studied in detail (Gregory *et al.*, 1998; de Vries and Visser, 2001; Pollet *et al.*, 2010; Vaaje-Kolstad *et al.*, 2010; Bugg *et al.*, 2011; Majumdar *et al.*, 2014; Beeson *et al.*, 2015 and Pollegioni *et al.*, 2015). However, the mechanism by which the microorganisms detect the substrate and initiate the overall process of enzyme production is still unsolved.

Some researchers have proposed that a low constitutive level of cellulase expression is responsible for the formation of an inducer from cellulose, amplifying the signal (Amore *et al.*, 2013). Others have suggested that the microorganisms initiate a starvation process, which could in turn activate cellulase expression (de Souza, 2013). It is also possible that an inducing sugar derived from carbohydrates may be released from the organism's cell wall, which acts as a de-repressing molecule for hydrolase induction. Despite the fact that the true mechanism behind natural cellulase production induction is still lacking, some individual molecules have been reported to induce production of hydrolases.

The fungus *T. reesei* is an impressive producer of cellulases and most studies concerning the regulation of cellulase genes have been performed in this species.

The most powerful inducer of cellulases in *T. reesei* is sophorose, a disaccharide composed of β -1, 2-linked glucose units. Sophorose appears to be formed from cellobiose through trans glycosylation activity by β -glucosidase (Gritzali, 1979; Vaheri *et al.*, 1979; Fowler and Brown, 1992). In addition to *T. reesei*, sophorose is also known to induce cellulase expression in *A. terreus* and *Penicillium purpurogenum* (Bisaria and Mishra, 1989; Hrmova *et al.*, 1991).

Another important inducer of cellulase is cellobiose (two β -1, 4-linked glucose units). It is formed as the end product of cellobiohydrolases activity. It has been reported to induce cellulase expression in many species of fungi, which include *T. reesei*, *Volvariella volvacea*, *P. janthinellum* and *A. nidulans* (Hrmova *et al.*, 1991; Mernitz *et al.*, 1996; Ilmen *et al.*, 1997; Chikamatsu *et al.*, 1999; Ding and Buswell, 2001).

Some studies concerning the inducing effect of cellobiose on cellulase expression are however controversial (Aro *et al.*, 2005). For instance, cellobiose can be trans glycosylated by β -glucosidases, producing sophorose, which could be the true inducer of cellulases. In addition, β -glucosidases are able to cleave the cellobiose into glucose, which may cause repression by carbon catabolite repression (CCR). Therefore, the outcome in cellobiose cultures appears to be dependent on the balance between hydrolysis and trans glycosylation, as well as the subsequent uptake of the generated sugars and the intracellular signals they initiate.

Interestingly the disaccharide lactose (1,4-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl-D-glucose), which is not a component of plant cell wall polymers, has been shown to be economically viable in inducing cellulase expression in *T. reesei*. Lactose induction of cellulase genes requires the β -anomer of D-galactose (Fekete *et al.*, 2008).

Hemicellulase expression has been studied mostly in *Aspergilli* and *T. reesei* (Pel *et al.*, 2007; Martinez, *et al.*, 2008). It is reported that the presence of the hemicelluloses xylan, xyloglucan, arabinan and mannan usually induces a high production of hemicellulases. However, just as for cellulases, the mechanism is unknown.

In most cases, small hemicellulose-derived molecules are able to induce the expression of a wide range of hemicellulases.

The monosaccharide D-xylose is a well-known inducer of xylanolytic enzymes as well as other hydrolase genes such as α -glucuronidase (agu A), acetylxylan esterase (axe A) and feruloyl esterase (faeA) in *Aspergillus* species (de Vries and Visser, 1999; de Vries *et al.*, 2002). Some studies have demonstrated that xylose can act as a repressor carbon source of hemicelluloses induction at high concentrations (de Vries *et al.*, 1999).

On the other hand, other studies have demonstrated that utilization of a high D-xylose concentration was beneficial for the induction of hemicelluloses-encoding genes (Mach-Aigner *et al.*, 2012). In addition to xylose, xylobiose and D-glucose- β -1, 2-D-xylose have been demonstrated to induce expression of xylanolytic genes in *A. terreus* (Hrmova *et al.*, 1991).

In *T. reesei*, the induction of hemicelluloses was observed during growth in the presence of cellulose, xylan, sophorose, xylobiose and L-arabitol (Aro *et al.*, 2005). For instance, a xylanase gene (xyn2) was induced by sophorose and xylobiose (Mach *et al.*, 1996; Zeilinger *et al.*, 1996). Xylobiose has also been reported to be able to induce genes involved in xylan degradation in *T. reesei*, such as the xylanase genes xyn1 and xyn2 and the β -xylosidase gene bxl1. In addition, sophorose induced some genes encoding enzymes that cleave the side chains of xylan such as agl1 and agl2 (α -galactosidase genes), and glr1, encoding a α -glucuronidase gene (Margolles-Clark *et al.*, 1997).

Complex mixtures of polysaccharides have also been shown to induce a wide range of cellulase and hemicelluloses genes in *A. niger*. A good example is sugarcane biogases, a by-product of sugarcane that has been shown to induce lignocellulolytic enzyme production (de Souza *et al.*, 2011).

Induction of ligninase production using carboxyl methylcellulose (CMC), filter paper (FP), beech wood xylan, *R. mucronata* wood dust, cellobiose and avicel cellulose was very poor in this study. There was generally low lignin modifying enzyme activity in both bacterial and fungal isolates. In our earlier work (Bosire *et al.*, 2013b), all the crude gut extracts from two of the woodborers in this study showed ligninolytic, cellulolytic and xylolytic (hemicellulolytic) activities. Generally, among the lignin modifying enzymes, there was a high lignin peroxidase activity in the crude gut extracts obtained from all the woodborers screened whereas laccase and manganese peroxidase activities were relatively lower. MnP activity ranged from $1.64 \pm 0.021\text{U/L}$ to $4.73 \pm 0.002\text{U/L}$. This was the lowest ligninolytic activity. It was followed by Lac activity ranging from $0.36 \pm 0.028\text{U/L}$ to $21.16 \pm 0.591\text{U/L}$. LiP activity was the highest ranging from $17.65 \pm 0.079\text{U/L}$ to $34.65 \pm 0.116\text{U/L}$. The highest ligninolytic activity (LiP activity of 34.65U/L) exhibited 68.9% discolouration. It was not clear whether the enzymes were produced by gut micro biota symbionts or they are endogeneous, produced by glands in the digestive tract. The fact that bacterial and fungal isolates in this study showed very low ligninolytic activities, implies that ligninolytic enzymes are endogenously produced in the digestive glands in the gut of the woodborer hosts while cellulases and hemicelluloses produced by the endosymbionts complete the digestive process into oligomers and monomers.

Conclusion

The study showed that bacterial and fungal strains of *Lysinibacilli* and *Aspergilli* used are highly potential and useful for β -glucosidase and xylanase production.

It is therefore concluded that *Lysinibacilli* and *Aspergilli* in this study present interesting advantages that make them good models for studying physiological approaches to enzyme production and lignocellulose degradation, including inhibition studies, with the aim of developing the key enzymes. Their genomic features and systematic studies on their enzyme systems need to be investigated to facilitate directed strain engineering for improved performance in degradation of plant biomass.

The natural ability of these bacteria and fungi to degrade cellulosic biomass, due their highly efficient enzymatic systems, is very attractive for the development of new strategies concerning industrial processes. It is evident that complete digestion of wood in the woodborers guts require both ligninolytic endogenous enzymes produced by host glands and cellulolytic as well as hemicellulolytic enzymes produced by the endosymbionts. Therefore, there is need for the elucidation of woodborers digestomics, which will define the collective pool of host and symbiont genes that collaborate to achieve a high-efficiency lignocellulose digestion. This study has shown that avicel cellulose, cellobiose and xylan beech wood were the highest inducers of cellulases and hemicelluloses. These substrates are therefore recommended for induction of production of these enzymes.

Lastly, the high efficiency of marine woodborers gut bioreactors makes them promising models for the industrial conversion of lignocellulose into microbial products, enzymes and enzyme combinations of potential value to biomass-based industries, such as cellulosic biofuel production.

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References

Acharya D K, Chabhadiya SB, Shah AJ, Shilpkar P, Acharya PB, Modi HA. 2010. Enzyme profiling of lignocellulolytic fungi. *International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences* **4(2)**, 443-449. ISSN: 1991-8631.

Amore A, Vincenza F. 2013. Regulation of Cellulase and Hemicellulase Gene Expression in Fungi. *Current Genomics* **14(4)**, 230-249. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2174/1389202911314040002>.

Aro N, Pakula T, Penttila M. 2005. Transcriptional regulation of plant cell wall degradation by filamentous fungi. *FEMS microbiology reviews* **29(4)**, 719-39. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.femsre.2004.11.006>.

Beeson WT, Vu VV, Span EA, Phillips CM, Marletta MA. 2015. Cellulose degradation by polysaccharide mono oxygenases. *Annual Reviews of Biochemistry* **84**, 923-946. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev-biochem060614-034439>.

Beguin P. 1990. Molecular Biology of Cellulose Degradation. *Annual Reviews of Microbiology* **44**, 219-48. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev.mi.44>.

Bisaria VS, Mishra S. 1989. Regulatory aspects of cellulase biosynthesis and secretion. *Critical Reviews in Biotechnology* **9(2)**, 61-103. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3109/07388558909040616>.

Bosire CM, Abubakar L, Ochanda J, Bosire, JO. 2013b. Lignocellulolytic activities of crude gut extracts of marine woodborers *Dicyathifer mannii* and *Sphaeroma terebrans*. *International Journal of Biosciences (IJB)* **3(12)**, 134-144. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12692/ijb/3.12.134-144>.

- Bosire CM, Bosire JO, Abubakar LU, Ochanda JO.** 2015. Impact of Marine Woodborers *Dicyathifer manni*, *Sphaeroma terebrans* and *Cirolana* sp. on the Mangroves of the Kenyan Coast. International Journal of Ecology and Environmental Sciences **41(1-2)**, 23-31. ISSN: 2320-5199.
- Bosire CM, Ochanda J, Abubakar L, Bosire JO.** 2013a. Culturable gut microbiota of marine wood boring invertebrates *Dicyathifer manni* (wright, 1866), *Sphaeroma terebrans* (Bate, 1866) and *Cirolana* sp. Journal of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences (JBES). **3(11)**, 12-20. ISSN: 2222-3045.
- Bugg TDH, Ahmad M, Hardiman EM, Rahmanpour R.** 2011. Pathways for degradation of lignin in bacteria and fungi. Natural Products Reports **28**, 1883-1896. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/c1n>.
- Busk PK, Lange L.** 2015. Classification of fungal and bacterial lytic polysaccharide mono oxygenases. BMC Genomics **16**, 368. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12864-015-1601-6>.
- Camarero S, Sarkar S, Ruiz DF, Martinez MJ, Martinez AT.** 1999. Description of a versatile peroxidase involved in the natural degradation of lignin that has both manganese peroxidase and lignin peroxidase substrate interaction sites. Journal of Biological Chemistry **274**, 10324-10330. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1074/jbc.274.15.10324>.
- Chen XA, Ishida N, Todaka N, Nakamura R, Maruyama J.** 2010. Promotion of efficient Saccharification of crystalline cellulose by *Aspergillus fumigatus* Swo1. Applied and Environmental Microbiology **76**, 2556-2561. ISSN:1098-5336.
- Chikamatsu G, Shirai K, Kato M, Kobayashi T, Tsukagoshi N.** 1999. Structure and expression properties of the endo-beta-1, 4-glucanase A gene from the filamentous fungus *Aspergillus nidulans*. FEMS Microbiology Letters **175(2)**, 239-45. ISSN:1574-6968.
- Chun SG, Kok TT, Keat TL, Subhash B.** 2010. Bio-ethanol from lignocellulose: Status, perspectives and challenges in Malaysia. Bioresource Technology **101**, 4834-4841.
- De Souza WR, de Gouvea PF, Savoldi M, Malavazi I, Bernardes LAD, Goldman MHS, et al.** 2011. Transcriptome analysis of *Aspergillus niger* grown on sugarcane bagasse. Biotechnology for Biofuels **4**, 40. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1754-6834-4-40>.
- De Souza WR.** 2013. Microbial Degradation of Lignocellulosic Biomass. In: Sustainable Degradation of Lignocellulosic Biomass-Techniques, Application and Commercialization. Intech 207-247. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/54325>.
- De Vries RP, van de Vondervoort PJ, Hendriks L, van de Belt M, Visser J.** 2002. Regulation of the alpha-glucuronidase-encoding gene (agu A) from *Aspergillus niger*. Molecular Genetics and Genomics **268(1)**, 96-102. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00438-002-0729-7>.
- De Vries RP, Visser J, de Graaff LH.** 1999. CreA modulates the XlnR-induced expression on xylose of *Aspergillus niger* genes involved in xylan degradation. Research in Microbiology **150(4)**, 281-5. ISSN: 0923-2508.
- De Vries RP, Visser J.** 1999. Regulation of the feruloyl esterase (fae A) gene from *Aspergillus niger*. Applied Environmental Microbiology **65(12)**, 5500-3. ISSN: 5500-5503. <http://aem.asm.org/content/65/12/5500>.
- De Vries RP, Visser J.** 2001. *Aspergillus* enzymes involved in degradation of plant cell wall polysaccharides. Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews **65(4)**, 497-522. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1128/MMBR.65.4.497-522.2001>.

- De Vries RP.** 2003. Regulation of *Aspergillus* genes encoding plant cell wall polysaccharide-degrading enzymes; relevance for industrial production. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* **61(1)**, 10-20.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00253-002-1171-9>.
- Denise BM, Maria LA, Elba B, Julio SAN, Sergio HK.** 1996. Colorimetric assay for lignin peroxidase activity determination using methylene blue as substrate. *Biotechnological Techniques* **10(4)**, 273-276.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF00184028>.
- Desai SS, Tennali GB, Channur N, Anup AC, Deshpande G, Azhar Murtuza BP.** 2011. Isolation of laccase producing fungi and partial characterization of laccase. *Biotechnology, Bioinformatics and Bioengineering* **1(4)**, 543-549. ISSN: 2249-9075.
- Ding SJ, Ge W, Buswell JA.** 2001. Endoglucanase I from the edible straw mushroom, *Volvariella volvacea*. Purification, characterization, cloning and expression. *European Journal of Biochemistry* **268(22)**, 5687-95. ISSN: 0014-2956.
- Fakoussa RM, Frost PJ.** 1999. *In vivo*-decolorization of coal-derived humic acids by laccase-excreting fungus *Trametes versicolor*. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* **52**, 60-65.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s002530051487>.
- Fekete E, Padra J, Szentirmai A, Karaffa L.** 2008. Lactose and D-galactose catabolism in the filamentous fungus *Aspergillus nidulans*. *Acta Microbiologica et Immunologica Hungarica* **55(2)**, 119-24.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1556/AMicr.55.2008.2.4>.
- Fowler T, Brown RD, Jr.** 1992. The *bgl1* gene encoding extracellular beta-glucosidase from *Trichoderma reesei* is required for rapid induction of the cellulase complex. *Molecular Microbiology* **6(21)**, 3225-35. ISSN:1365-2958.
- Galazka JM, Tian CG, Beeson WT, Martinez B, Glass NL, Cate JHD.** 2010. Cellodextrin. Transport in Yeast for Improved Biofuel Production. *Science* **330(6000)**, 84-6.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1192838>.
- Goldemberg J, Coelho ST.** 2004. Renewable energy - traditional biomass vs. modern biomass. *Energy Policy* **32(6)**, 711-4
[http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S03014215\(02\)00340-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S03014215(02)00340-3).
- Gregory ACE, O'Connell APO, Boldwell P.** 1998. Xylans. *Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering Reviews* **15**, 439-455.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02648725.1998.10647965>.
- Gritzali M, Brown RD Jr.** 1979. The cellulase system of *Trichoderma*: relationship between purified extracellular enzymes from induced or cellulose-grown cells. *Advances in Chemistry* **181**, 237-60.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ba-1979-0181.ch012>.
- Hahn-Hagerdal B, Karhumaa K, Fonseca C, Spencer-Martins I, Gorwa-Grauslund MF.** 2007. Towards industrial pentose-fermenting yeast strains. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* **74(5)**, 937-53
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00253-006-0827-2>.
- Himmel ME.** 2007. Biomass recalcitrance: engineering plants and enzymes for biofuels production. *Science* **315(5827)**, 804-807.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1137016>.
- Howard RL, Abotsi E, Jansen van Rensburg EL, Howard S.** 2003. Lignocellulose biotechnology: Issues of bioconversion and enzyme production. *African Journal of Biotechnology* **2(12)**, 602-619. ISSN: 1684-5315.
- Hrmova M, Petrakova E, Biely P.** 1991. Induction of cellulose- and xylan-degrading enzyme systems in *Aspergillus terreus* by homo- and heterodisaccharides composed of glucose and xylose. *Journal of General Microbiology* **137(3)**, 541-7.

- Ilmen M, Saloheimo A, Onnela ML, Penttila ME.** 1997. Regulation of cellulase gene expression in the filamentous fungus *Trichoderma reesei*. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* **63(4)**, 1298-306. ISSN:1098-5336.
- Jun-Seok, Soon-Chul P, Jin-Woo K, Jae CP, Sung-Min P, Jin-Suk L.** 2010. Production of bioethanol from lignocellulose: Status and perspectives in Korea. *Bioresource Technology* **101**, 4801-4805.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2009.12.059>.
- Lee J.** 1997. Biological conversion of lignocellulosic biomass to ethanol. *Journal of Biotechnology*, **56**, 1-24.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1656\(97\)00073-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1656(97)00073-4).
- Leonowicz A, Grzywnowickz K.** 1981. Quantitative estimation of laccase forms in some white-rot fungi using syringaldazine as a substrate. *Enzyme and Microbial Technology* **3**, 55-58.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-0229\(81\)90036-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-0229(81)90036-3).
- Libmond S, Savoie JM.** 1993. Degradation of wheat straw by a microbial community—stimulation by a polysaccharides complex. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* **40**, 567-74.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF00175749>.
- Lopez MJ, Vargas-García MC, Suárez-Estrella F, Nichols NN, Dien BS, Moreno J.** 2007. Lignocellulose-degrading enzymes produced by the ascomycete *Coniochaeta ligniaria* and related species: Application for a lignocellulosic substrate treatment. *Enzyme and Microbial Technology* **40**, 794-800.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enzmictec.2006.06.012>
- Lynd LR, Weimer PJ, van Zyl WH, Pretorius IS.** 2002. Microbial cellulose utilization: Fundamentals and Biotechnology. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews* **66(4)**, 739.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/MMBR.66.3.506-577.2002>.
- Mach RL, Strauss J, Zeilinger S, Schindler M, Kubicek CP.** 1996. Carbon catabolite repression of xylanase I (*xyn1*) gene expression in *Trichoderma reesei*. *Molecular Microbiology* **21(6)**, 1273-81.
<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.13652958.1996.00094.x>
- Mach-Aigner AR, Omony J, Jovanovic B, van Boxel AJ, de Graaff LH.** 2012. d-Xylose concentration-dependent hydrolase expression profiles and the function of CreA and XlnR in *Aspergillus niger*. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* **78(9)**, 3145-55.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.07772-11>.
- Madson PW, Tereck CD.** 2004. Lignocelluloses Feedstocks for Ethanol Production: The Ultimate Renewable Energy Source. In: *Ethanol as Transportation Fuel-Production Technology Developments*. 2004 AIChE Annual Meeting. Austin Texas.
- Majumdar S, Lukk T, Solbiati JO, Bauer S, Nair SK, Cronan JE, Gerlt JA.** 2014. Roles of small laccases from *Streptomyces* in lignin degradation. *Biochemistry* **53**, 4047-4058.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/bi500285t>.
- Margolles-Clark M, Ilmen M, Penttila M.** 1997. Expression patterns of 10 hemicelluloses genes from filamentous fungus *Trichoderma reesei* on various carbon sources. *Journal of Biotechnology* **57**, 167-79.
- Martinez D, Berka RM, Henrissat B, Saloheimo M, Arvas M, Baker SE, et al.** 2008. Genome sequencing and analysis of the biomass-degrading fungus *Trichoderma reesei* (syn. *Hypocrea jecorina*). *Nature Biotechnology* **26(5)**, 553-60.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt1403>.
- Mernitz G, Koch A, Henrissat B, Schulz G.** 1996. Endoglucanase II (EGII) of *Penicillium janthinellum*: cDNA sequence, heterologous expression and promoter analysis. *Current Genetics* **29(5)**, 490-5.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02221519>.

- Miller GL.** 1959. Use of dinitrosalicylic acid and reagent for determination of reducing sugars. *Analytical Chemistry* **31**, 426-428. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac60147a030>.
- Noratiqah K, Madihah Md S, Adibah Y, Chun SC.** 2016. Production of Lignocellulolytic Enzymes by Micro organisms Isolated from *Bulbitermes* sp. Termite Gut in Solid-State Fermentation. *Waste and Biomass Valorisation* **7(2)**, 357-371. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-015-9453-5>.
- Orth AB, Royse DJ, Tien M.** 1993. Ubiquity of lignin-degrading peroxidases among various wood-degrading fungi. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* **59**, 4017-23. ISSN: 0099-2240.
- Pauly M, Andersen LN, Kauppinen S, Kofod LV, York WS, Albersheim P, et al.** 1999. A xyloglucan-specific endo-beta-1,4-glucanase from *Aspergillus aculeatus*: expression cloning in yeast, purification and characterization of the recombinant enzyme. *Glycobiology* **9(1)**, 93-100. <https://doi.org/10.1093/glycob/9.1.93>.
- Payne CM, Knott BC, Mayes HB, Hansson H, Himmel ME, Sandgren M, Stahlberg J, Beckham GT.** 2015. Fungal cellulases. *Chemical Reviews* **115**, 1308-1448. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr500351c>.
- Pel HJ, de Winde JH, Archer DB, Dyer PS, Hofmann G, Schaap PJ, et al.** 2007. Genome sequencing and analysis of the versatile cell factory *Aspergillus niger* CBS 513.88. *Nature Biotechnology* **25(2)**, 221-31. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt1282>.
- Pillai NK.** 1961. Wood – boring Crustacea of India. Manager of Publications, Govt. of India. Press, New Delhi 61.
- Pollegioni L, Tonin F, Rosini E.** 2015. Lignin-degrading enzymes. *FEBS Journal* **282**, 1190-1213. <https://doi.org/10.1111/febs.13224>.
- Pollet A, Delcour JA, Courtin CM.** 2010. Structural determinants of the substrate specificities of xylanases from different glycoside hydrolase families. *Critical Reviews in Biotechnology* **30(3)**, 176-91. <https://doi.org/10.3109/07388551003645599>.
- Risna RA, Suhirman.** 2002. Ligninolytic enzyme production by Polyporaceae from Lombok, Indonesia. *Fungal Diversity* **9**, 123-134. ISSN:1560-2745.
- Sahay R, Yadav RS, Yadav KD.** 2008. Purification and Characterization of Extracellular Laccase Secreted by *Pleurotus sajor-caju* MTCC 141. *Chinese Journal of Biotechnology* **24(12)**, 2068-2073. ISSN:1042-749X.
- Salame TM, Knop D, Levinson D, Mabjeesh SJ, Yarden O.** 2012. Release of *Pleurotus ostreatus* Versatile-Peroxidase from Mn²⁺ + Repression Enhances Anthropogenic and Natural Substrate Degradation. *PLoS ONE* **7(12)**, e52446. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0052446>.
- Salmones D, Mata G.** 2002. Detection of Extracellular Enzymes Produced by *Pleurotus* spp Grown on Coffee Pulp. *Mushroom Biology and Mushroom Products*. Sanchez *et al.* (Eds) **105(3)**, 878-968. ISBN 968-878-105-3.
- Santhakumaran LN.** 1996. Marine wood-borers from mangroves along Indian Coasts. *Journal of Indian Academy of Wood Science* **26**, 1-14. ISSN: 0972-172X.
- Sherief AA, El-Tanash AB, Temraz AM.** 2010. Lignocellulolytic enzymes and substrate utilization during growth and fruiting of *Pleurotus ostreatus* on some solid wastes. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* **3**, 18-34. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3923/jest.2010.18.34>.
- Singh CS, Singh VK, Tiwari SP, Sharma R.** 2011. Ligninolytic activity and lignocelluloses degradation profiles by natural isolates of *Pleurotus flabellatus* during mushroom cultivation on rice straw. *Asian Journal of Experimental Biological Sciences* **2(1)**, 158-161. ISSN:2248-9223.

-
- Sun Y, Cheng JY.** 2002. Hydrolysis of lignocellulosic materials for ethanol production: a review. *Bioresource Technology* **83**, 1-11. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0960-8524\(01\)00212](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0960-8524(01)00212).
- Sunna A, Antranikian G.** 1997. Xylanolytic enzymes from fungi and bacteria. *Critical Reviews in Biotechnology* **17(1)**, 39-67. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3109/07388559709146606>.
- Tan KT, Lee KT, Mohamed AR.** 2008. Role of energy policy in renewable energy accomplishment: the case of second-generation bioethanol. *Energy Policy* **36**, 3360-3365. nISSN: 0301-4215.
- Tengerdy RP, Szakacs G.** 2003. Bioconversion of lignocelluloses in solid substrate fermentation. *Biochemical Engineering Journal* **13**, 169-179. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-703X\(02\)00129-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-703X(02)00129-8).
- Turner RD.** 1966. The Identification of Molluscan Borers. Report to the Governemnt of India. FAO Report No. TA. 2155, 30.
- Turner RD.** 1971. Identification of marine wood - boring molluscs. In: Jones, E.B.G. and Eltringham, S.K. (Eds). *Marine Borers, Fungi and Fouling Organisms*. OECD, Paris 17-64.
- Vaaje-Kolstad G, Westereng B, Horn SJ, Liu ZL, Zhai H, Sørli M, Eijsink VGH.** 2010. An oxidative enzyme boosting the enzymatic conversion of recalcitrant polysaccharides. *Science* **330**, 219-222. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1192231>.
- Vaheri M, Leisola M, Kauppinen V.** 1979. Transglycosylation products of cellulose system of *Trichoderma reesei*. *Biotechnology Technology* **1**, 696-9.
- Van den Brink J, de Vries RP.** 2011. Fungal enzyme sets for plant polysaccharide degradation. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* **91**, 1477-1492. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00253-011-3473-2>.
- Watanabe H, Tokuda G.** 2010. Cellulolytic systems in insects. *Annual Review of Entomology* **55**, 609-632. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-112408-085319>.
- Yadav P, Yadav KS, Yadav M, Singh VK.** 2009. Purification of lignin peroxidase from the juice of *Musa paradisiaca* stem. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry* **25(4)**, 1113-1116. ISSN: 0970-020X.
- Zeilinger S, Mach RL, Schindler M, Herzog P, Kubicek CP.** 1996. Different inducibility of expression of the two xylanase genes *xyn1* and *xyn2* in *Trichoderma reesei*. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* **271(41)**, 25624-9. ISSN: 0021-9258.